

Training Methods for Improving the Quality, Value and Loyalty of Fresh Graduates

Rakesh SITEPU¹, Arlina Nurbaity LUBIS²,
Endang Sulistya RINI³, Beby Karina F. SEMBIRING⁴

¹ Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, INDONESIA
rakeshsitepu@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0003-1181-1095

² Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, INDONESIA
arlinalubis10@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-0797-9632

³ Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, INDONESIA
endang.sulistya@usu.ac.id

ORCID: 0000-0003-4068-2168

⁴ Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, INDONESIA
beby@usu.ac.id

ORCID: 0000-0002-8066-0337

Article information

Submission	06/08/2024	Revision received	16/09/2024
Acceptance	22/09/2024	Publication date	22/10/2024

Keywords:

Training
Quality
Loyalty
Value
Fresh graduate

Abstract: Fresh graduates often face significant uncertainty due to the intangible complexities of employment, a lack of adequate service orientation, and delayed realization of long-term benefits. This study investigates the relationship between the quality of experiential value and its impact on the loyalty of young workers. The research was conducted on fresh graduates participating in a non-wage employment program in Medan City. A sample of 250 participants was selected using the quota sampling method. SmartPLS 3.0 was utilized for statistical analysis. The findings demonstrate that the benefits received positively and significantly influence the experiential value for young workers. Moreover, the study confirms that these benefits indirectly enhance loyalty through improvements in the perceived quality of the experience. The results highlight the importance of targeted training methods to foster the value, commitment, and long-term engagement of youths entering the workforce.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Yetiştirme
Kalite
Sadakat
Değer
Yeni mezun

Yeni Mezunların Kalitesini, Değerini ve Sadakatini Artırmaya Yönelik Eğitim Yöntemleri

Özet: Mezunlar, istihdamın soyut karmaşıklıkları, yeterli hizmet odaklılığının eksikliği ve uzun vadeli faydaların geç fark edilmesi nedeniyle önemli bir belirsizlikle karşı karşıya kalmaktadır. Bu çalışma, deneysel değer kalitesi ile genç çalışanların sadakati üzerindeki etkisi arasındaki ilişkiyi araştırmaktadır. Araştırma, Medan şehrinde ücret dışı istihdam programına katılan yeni mezunlar üzerinde gerçekleştirilmiştir. Kota örnekleme yöntemi kullanılarak 250 katılımcıdan oluşan bir örneklem seçilmiştir. İstatistiksel analiz için SmartPLS 3.0 kullanılmıştır. Bulgular, elde edilen faydaların genç çalışanlar için deneysel değeri pozitif ve anlamlı bir şekilde etkilediğini göstermektedir. Ayrıca, bu faydaların, deneyim kalitesinde yaşanan iyileşmeler aracılığıyla dolaylı olarak sadakati artırdığı doğrulanmıştır. Sonuçlar, iş gücüne yeni katılan gençlerin değer, bağlılık ve uzun vadeli katılımlarını artırmak için hedeflenen eğitim yöntemlerinin önemini vurgulamaktadır.

To Cite This Article: Sitepu, R., Lubis, A. N., Rini, E. S., & Sembiring, B. K. F. (2024). Training methods for improving the quality, value and loyalty of fresh graduates. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(2), 270–283. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13894325>

1. Introduction

Fresh-graduated employment is a state institution engaged in social insurance. Fresh graduates of employment were born as a transformation from social security for workers, better known as fresh graduates. Fresh graduates focus on creating value for Indonesian workers as a driving force for the nation's economy, as stated in the short and medium-term plans for the 2017-2021 Strategic Plan. The 2017-2021 Strategic Plan is prepared because it is seen as readiness, achievement, and changes in the organizational environment of the freshly graduated employment agency. In addition, another aspect that drives change is information technology as intellectual capital, which also affects the social security industry in terms of registering, paying, and making claims. The five years are divided into the foundation development stage (2017-2018) and the aggressive growth stage (2019-2021). Services for insurance companies, in this case, freshly graduated employment, in providing services need to have an element of experience and trust from the participants (Chen & Wang, 2009). In addition, participants face considerable uncertainty stemming from intangibles (intangibility), complexity, lack of service introduction, and long-term benefits. In this context, fresh graduates need to provide experiential value and quality. The experience that a person has is not a spontaneous thing but because of the process of creation. Services for insurance companies, in this case, freshly graduated employment, in providing services need to have an element of experience and trust from the participants (Chen & Wang, 2009). In addition, participants face considerable uncertainty stemming from intangibles (intangibility), complexity, lack of service introduction, and long-term benefits. In this context, fresh graduates must provide experiential value and quality.

The experience that a person has is not a spontaneous thing but because of the process of creation. Because everyone is different, the experience felt is also different. The experience is momentary and is only felt at the time of consumption; the experiential value perceived by the consumer will be attached to the consumer's memory defines the experience value in Wang and Tsai (2010) as the level of experience that helps consumers achieve their consumption goals. The value of experience is based on interactions that include direct use and appreciation of products and services. Quality of experience focuses on self-assessment and is more subjective. Chan and Baum (2007) state that the concept of experience quality includes participants' affective responses to the desired psychological benefits of the experience. In service quality, service performance is at the attribute level, while experience quality refers to psychological outcomes resulting from participant participation or interaction with the company.

The value of experience and quality of experience in this study is significant, reflecting participants' aspirations related to feelings and comfort. Participants accept a pleasant experience, and the other side rejects an unpleasant experience (Suroso, 2017). Experience positively influences participant loyalty, as evidenced by research conducted by Razanah *et al.* (2010) and Alkiani *et al.* (2013); meanwhile, regarding the influence of the quality of experience on the value of experience, where the dimensions of the value of experience are emotional and functional. This study synthesized the two variables of experience value and experience quality, thinking that emotional and functional values of good quality would provide a good experience for participants so that the excellent quality of participant experience will positively influence the loyalty of fresh graduated employment participants.

The 2017-2021 strategic plan is a revision of the 2014-2018 strategic work plan after considering the agency's organizational environment's readiness, achievements, and changes.

Another aspect that drives change is the trend of information technology as intellectual capital, which also affects the social security industry regarding registering, paying, and making claims. Recent industry reports show that one of the most important trends in technology development in the insurance industry is automation and customized claim settlement (Deloitte Digital, 2017). The global development of information technology is a challenge and an opportunity for fresh graduates to provide a better-quality experience value for its participants—the participants' perceived benefits (perceived usefulness) through information technology. Information technology has developed in the banking sector, where services are carried out online, and its use is more routine, but this does not apply to insurance (Gebert-Persson *et al.*, 2018). Participants' adoption and engagement rates with online insurance were substantially lower. Interactions between insurance companies and participants usually occur when the insurance company provides information on the company's services when checking requirements before signing a contract or during the claims process. Therefore, considering the different adoption of information technology between the insurance industry and other financial sectors, the marketing strategy settings that prioritize interactions that need to be developed by the insurance industry are different.

Service recovery actions taken by service providers are a response to service failures and the process by which service providers try to repair the failure (Kelley & Davis, 1994). Del Río-Lanza *et al.* (2009) research states that service failure does not always lead to customer dissatisfaction because most consumers can accept that things can sometimes go wrong, especially in service. Cheng *et al.* (2019) state that service recovery satisfaction is generally known in distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. The importance of satisfaction with service recovery arises from its goal of retaining dissatisfied customers who may be willing to change providers if they witness a poor recovery experience.

The gap in the phenomenon occurs because the customer satisfaction index value does not describe loyal membership in Medan. The customer satisfaction index carried out by fresh graduates does not cover service recovery satisfaction. According to research by Díaz *et al.* (2017), the service recovery strategy is directly and positively related to overall customer satisfaction. This study examines the satisfaction of service recovery on brand resonance directly and on loyalty indirectly through brand resonance. The originality of this study is that the authors develop experiential value quality variables by synthesizing the initial experiential value and experiential quality variables (Wu *et al.*, 2018). Next, the author focuses on the second variable, service recovery satisfaction, with the initial variables being service recovery and recovery satisfaction (Nikbin *et al.*, 2010). The two new variables synthesized by the author will further analyze the new variable satisfaction of service recovery on loyalty through brand resonance. Then, the new variable quality of experience value becomes a mediator of the effect of perceived benefits on loyalty and a moderator of the relationship between brand resonance and loyalty.

As a contribution to the development of science, this research fills the gap in previous studies. In research conducted by Wu *et al.* (2017), the effect of the quality of experience on the value of experience, where the dimensions of the value of experience are emotional and functional, has inconsistencies, so in this study, we will examine the level of benefits of fresh graduated employment websites and applications that have been built since 2017. Based on the background above, the writer wants to research and analyze the quality of experiential value, which directly affects customer loyalty and influences brand resonance. Meanwhile, brand resonance is influenced by service recovery satisfaction. This study also analyses the

effect of perceived usefulness on the quality of the experience value of the non-wage recipient (BPU) program workers in Medan City.

1.1. Literature Review

1.1.1. *The effect of service recovery satisfaction on brand resonance*

Brand equity is significant for the service sector. Service industries such as financial services are facing increasingly fierce competition. The importance of brand equity in services can be seen from the perspective of service providers and consumers. With brand equity, the service industry provides a differential advantage that allows the company to generate greater profits, including greater customer loyalty and protects the company. In addition, brand equity creates better consumer response to price increases and decreases, more significant trade, and increased marketing communications and brand extension effectiveness. Brand resonance focuses on customers' primary relationship and level of identification with the brand. Brand resonance is a relationship between consumers and brands or an enhancement of consumer relationships with brands, and there is a difference in the potential for the emotional resonance of consumers to brands. Therefore, brand resonance refers to the nature of consumers' relationship, which indicates the relationship between the brand and the consumer and the degree to which consumers are aligned with the brand.

Every service organization tries to prevent service failure to save costs incurred in repairing it. However, various situations and conditions cause every element of the organization to be unable to avoid service failure. On the other hand, organizational response or lack of response to service failure is the cause of dissatisfaction. Therefore, this study will examine whether participants' satisfaction with service recovery will positively and significantly affect brand resonance.

H1: Service recovery satisfaction positively and significantly affects brand resonance.

1.1.2. *The effect of brand resonance on loyalty*

Brand loyalty started in the form of brand involvement, which states that customer attitudes to a brand are strengthened from those based on brand recognition to brand preferences and, finally, brand involvement. Then, in conceptual development, brand loyalty goes through two approaches: the traditional and the multidimensional (Suhartanto, 2011). The traditional approach begins with a behavioral, attitude, and combined approach. Loyalty with a behavioral approach refers to aspects of consumer behavior directed at certain brands over time or repeated purchases of brands. The attitudinal loyalty matrix follows the statement of preference and likelihood of future behavior and concerns with loyalty and engagement. Composite measures emerge by combining behavior and attitudes. However, composite loyalty is well excluded.

Loyalty is not limited to the customer's willingness to re-purchase a product or service but also the customer's willingness to recommend the brand to others and defend the brand when attacked (Fugeta, 2012). The importance of brand equity in services can be seen from the perspective of service providers and consumers. With brand equity, the service industry provides a differential advantage that allows the company to generate greater profits, including greater customer loyalty and protects the company's offerings from competitive attacks (Berry, 2000). Brand resonance denotes a deep consumer-brand relationship based on loyalty, attachment, and a long-lasting sense of similarity or affiliation. This relationship

is powerful in the desire of members of the brand community, willing to invest (invest money) in their resources to stay in touch with the brand.

According to Keller (2003), resonance is characterized as the intensity, or depth, of the psychological bond that customers have with the brand, as well as the level of activity that this loyalty has bound (e.g., the level of repeat purchases and the more customers seek out information about the brand, the activities they engage in). and other loyal customers). The resonance of a brand itself can be seen on two sides. First is intensity, namely the depth of the psychological bond between customers and a brand. It is what we often call loyalty. Second, the high activity is driven by this loyalty. Starting from how much he made a product purchase and how often the purchase was made. Specifically, Keller (2003) divides brand resonance into four categories: behavioral loyalty, attitudinal attachment, sense of community, and active engagement. Behavioral loyalty is a behavior that shows loyalty to a brand. What is this behavior like? Of course, by making a purchase. Research by Hwai-Shuh and Wei-Hsun (2017) shows that brand resonance positively and significantly affects loyalty.

H2: Brand resonance has a positive and significant effect on loyalty

1.1.3. The effect of perceived benefits on the quality of experience value

The experience is momentary and is only felt at the time of consumption; the experiential value perceived by the consumer will be attached to the consumer's memory. The experience value in Wang and Tsai (2010) is the level of experience that helps consumers achieve their consumption goals. The value of experience is based on interactions that include direct use and appreciation of products and services. Quality of experience focuses on self-assessment and is more subjective. Chan and Baum (2007) state that the concept of experience quality includes participants' affective responses to the desired psychological benefits of the experience. In service quality, service performance is at the attribute level, while experience quality refers to psychological outcomes resulting from participant participation or interaction with the company. The value of experience and quality of experience in this study is significant, reflecting participants' aspirations related to feelings and comfort. Participants accept a pleasant experience, and the other side rejects an unpleasant experience (Suroso, 2017). Experience positively influences participant loyalty, as evidenced by research conducted by Razanah *et al.* (2010) and Alkiani *et al.* (2013). Meanwhile, regarding the influence of the quality of experience on the value of experience, where the dimensions of the value of experience are emotional and functional, there are inconsistencies in the research results conducted by Wu and Li (2017).

Recent industry reports show that one of the most important trends in technology development in the insurance industry is automation and customized claim settlement (Deloitte Digital, 2017). The global development of information technology is a challenge and an opportunity for fresh graduates to provide a better quality experience value for their participants. The insurance industry increasingly uses digital technology and the internet as a channel for communication, interaction, and distribution. It causes insurance companies to encourage participants to use online insurance services actively. Information technology has developed in the banking sector, where services are carried out online, and its use is more routine, but this does not apply to insurance (Gebert-Persson *et al.*, 2018). As a result, participants' adoption and engagement rates with online insurance were substantially lower. Interactions between insurance companies and participants usually occur when the insurance company provides information on the company's service check requirements before signing a contract or during the claims process. Therefore, considering the different adoption of

information technology between the insurance industry and other financial sectors, the marketing strategy settings that prioritize interactions that need to be developed by the insurance industry are different. This study will test whether the benefits received by participants have a positive and significant effect on the quality of the experience value of fresh employment participants.

H3: The benefits received positively and significantly affect the quality of the experience value.

1.1.4. The effect of quality experience value on loyalty

The level of customer loyalty is a process that has continued to develop since the 1970s. Loyalty is a goal for strategic market planning in the long term and is also used as the basis for developing a sustainable competitive advantage (Dick & Basu, 1994) which is an advantage that can be realized through marketing efforts. Oliver (1999) and Kotler (2003) define brand loyalty as a deep commitment to re-purchase or re-subscribe to a selected product or service in the future. Buying the same brand repeatedly or buying the same group of brands repeatedly despite situational influences and marketing efforts could cause behavior to change. At the same time, Wernerfelt (1991) states that loyalty is an asset where consumers are willing to pay more to get the goods or services offered.

Loyalty is a fundamental concept in marketing strategy as it can create advantages in marketing, namely word-of-mouth referrals and resistance to increasing competition. Brand loyalty is a condition where consumers have a positive attitude towards a brand, are committed to the brand, and intend to continue purchasing. Brand loyalty in consumers is caused by the influence of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the brand, which accumulates continuously in addition to the perception of product quality.

Retention (memory or memory), advocacy, and wallet sharing indicate the dimensionalization of customer brand loyalty. Experiences result from stimulation and lead to pleasurable outcomes, hoping consumers will want to repeat them. This means that the quality of the value experience must influence consumer judgments directed not only at the past but also at consumer loyalty directed at the future. Consumers are more likely to re-purchase and recommend the brand, and the tendency to buy alternative brands is decreasing (Oliver, 1999).

According to Schmitt (1999), experiences are private events that occur in response to some stimulation (e.g., provided by marketing efforts before and after purchase), which means that experience is a personal event that occurs in response to some stimulus (effort exerted by marketing before and after purchase). Several studies on the impact of customer value on loyalty suggest that higher customer value enhances a company's ability to retain customers.

H4: Quality of experience value positively and significantly affects loyalty.

1.1.5. The effect of service recovery satisfaction on loyalty through brand resonance

Loyalty is characterized by a deep commitment to re-purchasing a product or service. Brand loyalty shows that satisfaction maintenance is associated with retaining the brand by becoming a loyal customer through favorable comments (Bloemer & Kasper, 1995). Del Río-Lanza *et al.* (2009) research states that service failure does not always lead to customer dissatisfaction because most consumers can accept that things can sometimes go wrong, especially in service. On the other hand, organizational response or lack of response to

service failure is the cause of dissatisfaction. Service recovery refers to the actions taken by the company when it experiences a service failure or service failure. However, there are still many companies that do not do this. At the same time, the service recovery strategy has a significant impact, ranging from direct customer response to customer loyalty. Therefore, service recovery procedures are crucial for companies to achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Customer satisfaction after a service failure can influence consumers to re-consumption and spread negative word-of-mouth. Both behaviors can indicate customer satisfaction and restore customer loyalty to the service. Many factors underlie the assessment of customer satisfaction that causes loyalty. For example, customer satisfaction with services is influenced by service quality, which comes from assessing the quality of results, interactions, and the physical environment. On the other hand, customer satisfaction with service recovery by a company or service provider depends on how the customer perceives justice when his complaint is handled. This study will test whether service recovery satisfaction positively and significantly affects loyalty through brand resonance.

H5: Service recovery satisfaction positively and significantly affects loyalty through brand resonance.

1.1.6. The effect of perceived benefits on loyalty through experience quality values

Perceived usefulness is how much a person believes technology will improve their performance. From this definition, perceived benefit is a belief in decision-making. Generally, humans will use an application if it helps and facilitates their work.

Ramayah (2006) identifies the four dimensions for measuring perceived usefulness. Accordingly, usefulness refers to the degree to which technology facilitates tasks. Efficiency refers to the extent to which technology accelerates task completion, emphasizing execution speed. The third one is the advantage, meaning the benefits of utilizing the technology. Lastly, effectiveness refers to the capacity of technology to enhance an individual's performance, particularly in terms of time savings experienced by the user.

Customer value is “interactive,” where value is the reciprocal interaction between the customer and the product/service. Value is derived from the attributes, qualities, or benefits of a product/service and occurs when customers value them. Second, customer value is relativistic. In other words, customer value is product/service comparative, person-to-person, and situational or context-specific. Value assessment involves preferences among products/services, and customers perceive value in a particular product/service by comparing different attributes among products/services and identifying relative preferences among them. Customer value is personal because the perceived value of the same product/service varies from customer to customer. In addition, customer value is situational because the perceived value of the product/service is specific to the context and varies from time to time, from place to place, or from time to time.

Furthermore, customer value is “preferential” because it involves judgmental preferences, including “effect (favorable-disappointing), attitude (like-dislike), evaluation (good-bad), inclination (favorable-unfavorable), opinion (pro-con), response propensity (approach-avoidance), or valence (positive-negative). Finally, customer value is “an experience.” Value is not attached to the product/service or brand but to the consumption and experience that comes from it. At the same time, brand loyalty statements in the form of brand involvement

state that customer attitudes to a brand are strengthened from those based on brand recognition to brand preferences and, finally, brand involvement. Then, in conceptual development, brand loyalty is achieved through traditional and multidimensional approaches.

H6: Perceived benefits significantly and positively affect loyalty through the quality of experience values.

2. Method

This research is quantitative, systematic scientific research on parts and phenomena. In this study, the population is all active fresh graduated employment non-wage recipient (BPU) program workers who were domiciled in the Medan City area in 2021, with 24,291 participants. The sample size in this study was adjusted to the analytical model used, namely the structural equation model (SEM). According to Ferdinand (2014), the ratio of the number of samples to indicators is 5:1. In this study; there were 50 indicators from five variables, so the study sample was $50 \times 5 = 250$ participants spread over 21 sub-districts in the city of Medan. Interval data can be generated in various ways, including using a Likert scale. A Likert-type scale is used for five values. This study uses the analysis tool SmartPLS version 3. Codes for variables include 1) Service Recovery Satisfaction = KP; 2) Quality of Experiential value = KN; 3) Loyalty = L; 4) Beneficiary = MYD; 5) Brand Resonance = RM.

2. Findings and Discussion

Two methods were used to test the construct validity: convergent and discriminant. The results of convergent validity are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Convergent Validity

Variable	AVE
KP	0.906
KN	0.900
L	0.815
MYD	0.880
RM	0.901

Source: Data Processed (2021)

The evaluation of the outer and inner models of the SEM-PLS test will be described to obtain an empirical model based on the underlying assumptions. Furthermore, the assumption of convergent validity is carried out on the assessment ($AVE > 0.50$). The AVE results show that the AVE value of KPL, KNE, LYT, PM, and RM is >0.50 . The results of discriminant validity (cross-loadings) are presented in Table 2.

The results of the cross-loadings show that all items assigned based on their respective constructs meet the cross-loading method and the assumption of discriminant validity because each item reflected in their correlated constructs is greater than the correlation of other constructs items. Furthermore, it can be seen that the reliability results of all constructs are reliable because the constructs mentioned above are above 0.70. Therefore, the composite reliability value of each construct is expected to be at least 0.7. The SmartPLS algorithm's results on each construct's composite reliability are presented in Table 3.

Table 2.
Discriminant Validity

	KN	KP	L	MYD	RM		KN	KP	L	MYD	RM
KN1	0.862	0.825	0.788	0.845	0.839	L2	0.696	0.697	0.816	0.716	0.707
KN10	0.879	0.807	0.733	0.835	0.807	L3	0.716	0.713	0.822	0.697	0.700
KN11	0.913	0.840	0.805	0.851	0.820	L4	0.745	0.710	0.829	0.705	0.737
KN12	0.925	0.849	0.811	0.888	0.867	L5	0.720	0.690	0.785	0.690	0.705
KN2	0.905	0.827	0.808	0.877	0.854	L6	0.809	0.746	0.834	0.775	0.758
KN3	0.900	0.852	0.819	0.858	0.843	L7	0.712	0.718	0.843	0.680	0.698
KN4	0.914	0.810	0.794	0.855	0.848	L8	0.821	0.796	0.862	0.804	0.790
KN5	0.911	0.833	0.798	0.864	0.871	L9	0.691	0.671	0.798	0.671	0.647
KN6	0.894	0.839	0.814	0.861	0.861	MYD1	0.861	0.828	0.781	0.879	0.847
KN7	0.920	0.849	0.856	0.872	0.865	MYD10	0.789	0.750	0.651	0.817	0.759
KN8	0.874	0.811	0.778	0.837	0.844	MYD2	0.840	0.856	0.762	0.887	0.858
KN9	0.901	0.875	0.819	0.875	0.872	MYD3	0.840	0.838	0.807	0.861	0.839
KP1	0.799	0.876	0.760	0.826	0.818	MYD4	0.848	0.845	0.746	0.895	0.887
KP10	0.866	0.921	0.793	0.865	0.860	MYD5	0.822	0.813	0.803	0.866	0.829
KP11	0.830	0.916	0.795	0.858	0.856	MYD6	0.836	0.827	0.746	0.900	0.843
KP12	0.830	0.897	0.745	0.852	0.872	MYD7	0.836	0.872	0.756	0.898	0.855
KP2	0.852	0.925	0.804	0.854	0.853	MYD8	0.844	0.827	0.779	0.905	0.842
KP3	0.835	0.888	0.815	0.829	0.858	MYD9	0.892	0.832	0.817	0.893	0.828
KP4	0.846	0.906	0.778	0.863	0.855	RM1	0.867	0.869	0.808	0.871	0.902
KP5	0.837	0.908	0.795	0.851	0.851	RM10	0.866	0.861	0.793	0.874	0.938
KP6	0.825	0.902	0.776	0.841	0.840	RM2	0.827	0.836	0.766	0.857	0.878
KP7	0.856	0.912	0.797	0.862	0.883	RM3	0.869	0.845	0.813	0.844	0.869
KP8	0.835	0.925	0.784	0.870	0.863	RM4	0.835	0.818	0.760	0.844	0.882
KP9	0.875	0.897	0.849	0.869	0.843	RM5	0.858	0.864	0.800	0.849	0.885
L1	0.669	0.722	0.731	0.705	0.716	RM6	0.843	0.833	0.777	0.851	0.905
L10	0.698	0.673	0.774	0.679	0.686	RM7	0.838	0.846	0.772	0.854	0.911
L11	0.688	0.656	0.787	0.635	0.628	RM8	0.839	0.858	0.786	0.854	0.923
L12	0.729	0.730	0.883	0.729	0.730	RM9	0.855	0.859	0.771	0.882	0.909

Table 3.
Reliability Result

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
KP	0.980	0.980	0.982	0.821
KN	0.979	0.979	0.981	0.810
L	0.954	0.955	0.959	0.664
MYD	0.968	0.968	0.972	0.775
RM	0.974	0.974	0.977	0.811

This shows that each construct met the outer model reliability assessment criteria with a composite reliability value of > 0.7. the value of the coefficient R2 for each variable in this study.

Table 4.
R Square Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
KN	0.913	0.913
L	0.811	0.809
RM	0.889	0.889

The hypothesis in this study will be tested statistically using the bootstrap method. Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the path coefficient value, which indicates the significance level of hypothesis testing. The path coefficient score indicated by the T-statistic

value must be greater than the one-way test t-table value (>1.64) with $\alpha = 5\%$. In addition, the p-values must be below $\alpha = 0.05$ so that the research hypothesis proposed in the study can be accepted.

Table 5.
Hypotheses Direct Effect

Hypotheses	Variables	T statistic	Decision
H1	KP -> RM	42.580	Accepted
H2	RM -> L	0.800	Not Accepted
H3	MY -> KN	58.502	Accepted
H4	KN -> L	3.187	Accepted
H5	KP $\square$ RM $\square$ L	0.800	Not Accepted
H6	MYD $\square$ KN $\square$ L	3.167	Accepted

Based on the results of testing hypothesis 1, it was found that Service Recovery Satisfaction affects Brand Resonance. Service recovery actions taken by service providers are a response to service failures and the process by which service providers try to repair the failure. Cheng et al. (2019) state that satisfaction with service recovery is generally known in three ways: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. The importance of restoring service satisfaction arises from its goal of retaining dissatisfied customers who may be willing to change providers if they witness a poor recovery experience.

This study synthesizes the theory of service recovery and recovery satisfaction, forming a new variable: service recovery satisfaction. This study will measure participant satisfaction with service recovery by fresh graduates. Service recovery satisfaction in this study uses the results of the synthesis of both theories, each of which has dimensions, namely perceived justice, distribution justice, procedural justice, interactional justice, and consumption satisfaction scale. The brand relationship is a resonance brand that describes the nature of this relationship and the extent to which feelings related to consumer satisfaction range that they are aligned with the brand. Brand resonance focuses on customers' primary relationship and level of identification with the brand. Brand resonance is characterized by intensity or depth and the level of activity that develops in loyalty. In customer-based brand equity (CBBE), brand resonance is a relationship between consumers and brands or the enhancement of consumer relationships with brands, and there is a difference in the potential for the emotional resonance of consumers to brands. Brand resonance refers to the nature of consumers' relationship, which indicates the relationship between the brand and the consumer and the degree to which consumers are aligned with the brand. The brand resonance model shows that brand resonance, for example, brand loyalty, can be achieved through two routes, namely rational and emotional. The rational route includes essential components, such as performance (e.g., price, efficiency, durability, reliability) and judgments (e.g., quality, credibility). In contrast, those include emotions, such as images and feelings (e.g., pleasure, excitement).

Loyal behavior can be seen in how often customers buy the brand and how much they buy. Customers must generate sufficient frequency and volume of purchases to generate sufficient profit. However, another element, namely a Sense of community, is where the brand has a broader meaning for customers. Identification with the brand community can reflect an important social phenomenon in which customers feel a sense of kinship or affiliation with others associated with the brand. These connections may involve fellow brand users, customers, or vice versa, employees with company representatives. According to McMillan & Chavis (1986), a sense of community is a feeling wherein a group of people feel belonging

and interdependent, and believe their needs will be met through a shared commitment. Departing from this is the reason that hypothesis 2 is rejected.

From the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that hypothesis 3 was accepted. Davis *et al.* (1989) found that perceived benefits had a stronger and more consistent effect on the acceptance of information technology than other variables, such as attitudes, satisfaction, and other perceived measures. The results of a study showed similar findings, where the relationship between perceived usefulness and use of information systems was positive. Davis *et al.* (1989) showed that perceived usefulness was a significant determinant of acceptance. In contrast, another indicated that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly influenced someone to accept the new system. At the same time, the value of experience is defined as the degree to which experience helps consumers achieve their consumption goals. Experiential value is based on interaction, including direct use and appreciation of products and services. The value of experience is a personal event generated in response to a stimulus arising from direct interaction with a product or service or through active participation in the consumption process. Multidimensional customer value captures various aspects of the consumption experience. Fresh graduated employment customers value an interactive relativistic experience preference and emphasize four basics of customer value: interactive, relativistic, preferential, and experiential.

Furthermore, to support the finding that hypothesis 4 is accepted, Oliver (2014) states that customer loyalty is a deep commitment to re-subscribe or re-purchase selected products/services consistently in the future despite the influence of situations and efforts. Marketing efforts have the potential for behavior change. Meanwhile, loyalty is aimed at behavior aimed at repeat purchases and recommending the company's products to friends or partners. The multidimensional approach to loyalty occurred when Oliver (1999) pioneered his concept of brand loyalty. Brand loyalty is a deep commitment to re-purchase or repeat the preferred product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing the same brand or the same brand purchase, regardless of situational influences and marketing efforts that have the potential to cause switching behavior (Oliver, 2010). In addition, it emphasizes switching behavior, where the measure of loyalty must refer to consumer interest in the brand and the vulnerability of fresh graduated labor consumers to switch.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that hypothesis 5 was rejected. Many factors underlie the assessment of customer satisfaction that causes loyalty. Customer satisfaction with services is influenced by service quality, which comes from assessing the quality of results, interactions, and the physical environment. However, service recovery satisfaction has directly affected loyalty, according to the statistical results of this study. Based on these results, the researcher found that brand resonance failed to mediate the relationship between service recovery satisfaction and loyalty. This is because both brand resonance and Service Recovery Satisfaction directly affect loyalty. Consumers have felt a sense of satisfaction without brand resonance, so they directly behave loyally to freshly graduated labor services.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that hypothesis 6 was accepted. Experience value refers to the customer's perception of a product or service through direct use or indirect observation (Mathwick *et al.*, 2001). Customers can derive experience value from different types of experiences. Compared to customer value, experience value focuses on the value the customer gets and feels from this experience. However, research on the value of experience is limited (Wu & Liang, 2009; Yuan & Wu, 2008). The measurement of the value of experience developed in this study is based on the functional and emotional

features of freshly graduated labor members, which are the main components of the experience value, as suggested by Yuan and Wu (2008). In general, functional value can be considered as the primary value delivered to customers (Berry et al., 2002; Schmitt, 1999)

In addition, emotional value refers to the feelings or reactions visitors get during and after experiencing (Berry et al., 2002; Schmitt, 1999). To fully understand the various functions of experience value in regulatory services, it is necessary to find the relationship between experience value, quality, and consumer satisfaction of freshly graduated labor. Formulate experiential value as a direct consequence of perceived quality, price-based transactions, and acquisition utility. The perception of experiential value is strongly associated with the interaction between the use and evaluation of remote quality, and this interaction provides the basis for the perception of experiential value. Lee and Bang (2004) examined online shopping and proposed that the value of the experience positively affects satisfaction.

3. Conclusion

This study uncovers several key findings. First, satisfaction with service recovery has a positive and significant impact on brand resonance. However, brand resonance does not appear to influence loyalty significantly. Additionally, the benefits received positively and meaningfully affect the quality of experiential value, which, in turn, has a significant positive impact on loyalty. It is also noted that satisfaction with service recovery does not influence loyalty through brand resonance, whereas the benefits received enhance loyalty through improvements in experiential value. These insights have important implications for recent graduates' education and professional development. While enhancing service recovery efforts may strengthen brand resonance, loyalty is more strongly shaped by the perceived quality of experiential value than by brand resonance alone.

To support fresh graduates in their transition to the workforce, educational institutions and employers should focus on designing programs that offer tangible benefits and cultivate valuable experiential learning opportunities. By improving the quality of these experiences, institutions can help foster greater loyalty, trust, and long-term engagement among young professionals. Future research should expand this study's scope by testing the alignment of these variables in a broader geographic context, enabling more generalized and factual conclusions. Moreover, continuous improvements in service recovery performance and benefit offerings will strengthen fresh graduates' consistency, commitment, and professional growth as they integrate into the labor market.

Note on Ethical Issues

Ethical permission for this study was attained from Universitas Sumatera Utara's Ethical Committee on 10/01/2023 with decision number 39/UN5.1.R/SK/SSA/2023

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

Alkiani, K., Choon, L. K., & Abzakh, A. A. (2013). The impact of experiential marketing and customer satisfaction on customer commitment in social networks. *Asian Social Science*, 9(1), 262–270. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n1p262>

- Berry, L. L., Carbone, L. P., & Haeckel, S. H. (2002). Managing the total customer experience. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 43(3), 1–6.
- Bloemer, J. M. M., & Kasper, H. D. P. (1995). The complex relationship between consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 16, 311–329. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-4870\(95\)00007-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-4870(95)00007-B)
- Chan, J. K. L., & Baum, T. (2007). Ecotourists' perception of ecotourism experience in lower Kinabatangan, Sabah, Malaysia. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 15(5), 574–590. <https://doi.org/10.2167/jost679.0>
- Chen, M., & Wang, L. (2009). The moderating role of switching barriers on customer loyalty in the life insurance industry. *The Service Industries Journal*, 29(8), 1105–1123. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02642060902764574>
- Cheng, B. L., Gan, C. C., Imrie, B. C. & Mansori, S. (2019). Service recovery, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Evidence from Malaysia's hotel industry. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 11(2), 187–203. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQSS-09-2017-0081>
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw P. R (1989). User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical model. *Management Science*, 35(8), 982–1003.
- Del Río-Lanza, A. B., Vázquez-Casielles, R., & Díaz-Martín, A M. (2009). Satisfaction with service recovery: Perceived justice and emotional responses. *Journal of Business Research Volume* 62(8), 775–781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2008.09.015>
- Deloitte Digital (2017). *From mystery to mastery: unlocking the business value of artificial intelligence in the insurance industry*. Deloitte Insurance Tech: Germany.
- Díaz, E., Gómez, M., Martín-Consuegra, D., & Molina, A. (2017). The effects of perceived satisfaction with service recovery efforts: a study in a hotel setting. *Marketing and Tarde*, 4, 203–218. <https://doi.org/10.15240/tul/001/2017-4-014>.
- Dick, A. S., & Basu, K. (1994). Customer loyalty: Toward an integrated conceptual framework. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 22, 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070394222001>
- Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Metode penelitian manajemen*. Seri Pustaka Kunci: Semarang.
- Fugeta, R. (2012). *Brand advocates: Turning Enthusiastic customer into a powerful marketing force*. New Jersey: Jhon Wiley & Son.
- Gebert-Persson, S., Gidhagen, M., Sallis, J. E., & Lundberg, H. (2019). Online insurance claims: When more than trust matters. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 37(2), 579–594. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-02-2018-0024>
- Hwai-Shuh, S., & Wei-Hsun, L. (2017). The relationships among brand experience, brand resonance and brand loyalty in experiential marketing: Evidence from smart phone in Taiwan. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 28(2), 57–73. <https://doi.org/10.22367/jem.2017.28.04>
- Keller, K. (2003). Understanding brands, branding and brand equity. *Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice*, 5, 7–20. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.im.4340213>
- Kelley, S. W., & Davis, M. A. (1994). Antecedents to customer expectations for service recovery. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 22(1), 52–61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070394221005>
- Kotler, P. (2003). *Marketing insights from A to Z: 80 concepts every manager needs to know*. New Jersey: John Wiley.
- Lee, C. S., & Bang, S. B. (2004). The effects of shopping value on online purchasing intention: Focus on product attribute importance as intervening variables. *Korean Marketing Research*, 19(2), 41–69.

- Mathwick, C., Malhotra, N., & Rigdon, E. (2001). Experiential value: Conceptualization, measurement and application in the catalog and internet shopping environment. *Journal of Retailing*, 77(1), 39–56. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(00\)00045-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(00)00045-2)
- Nikbin, D., Ismail, I., Marimuthu, M., & Jalalkamali, M. (2010). Perceived justice in service recovery and recovery satisfaction: The moderating role of corporate image. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 2(2), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v2n2p47>
- Oliver, R. (1999). Whence consumer loyalty? *The Journal of Marketing*, 63, 33–44. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1252099>
- Oliver, R. (2010). Consumer brand loyalty. In J. Sheth & N. Malhotra (Eds), *International Encyclopedia of Marketing*. New York: Wiley.
- Oliver, R. (2014). *Satisfaction: A behavioral perspective on the consumer*. New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315700892>
- Ramayah, T. (2006). Course website usage: Does prior experience matter? *WSEAS Transactions on Information Science and Applications*, 2(3), 299–306.
- Razanah, Z., Kumaji, K., & Kusumawati, A. (2010). Penerapan experiential marketing strategy dan pengaruhnya terhadap kepuasan dan loyalitas (studi pada pelanggan bakso cak kar singosari – malang). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 5(2), 1–8. Retrieved from <https://administrasibisnis.studentjournal.ub.ac.id/index.php/jab/article/view/245>
- Schmitt, B. H., (1999). *Experiential marketing: How to get customers to sense, feel, think, act, and relate to your company and brands*. New York: Free Press.
- Suroso, I. (2017). Building customer loyalty based on service quality, company image, customer value and experiential marketing. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15(17), 285–298. Retrieved from https://repository.unej.ac.id/jspui/bitstream/123456789/83698/1/F.%20EB_Jurnal_Imam%20S_Building%20Customer.pdf
- Wang, C. C., & Tsai, C. Y. (2010). Customized interface design of the intelligent PDA for e-learning. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(14), 2941–2951.
- Wernerfelt, B. (1991). Brand loyalty and market equilibrium. *Marketing Science*, 10(3), 229–245. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.10.3.229>
- Wu, C. H. J., & Liang, R. D. (2009). Effect of experiential value on customer satisfaction with service encounters in luxury-hotel restaurants. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 28(4), 586–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2009.03.008>
- Wu, H.-C., & Li, T. (2017). A study of experiential quality, perceived value, heritage image, experiential satisfaction, and behavioral intentions for heritage tourists. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 41(8), 904–944. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348014525638>
- Wu, H.-C., Li, M.-Y., & Li, T. (2018). A study of experiential quality, experiential value, experiential satisfaction, theme park image, and revisit intention. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 42(1), 26–73 <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348014563396>
- Yuan, Y. H. E., & Wu, C. K. (2008). Relationships among experiential marketing, experiential value, and customer satisfaction. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 32, 387–410. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348008317392>